

Original Article

Publication History:
Received 20/5/2020
Accepted 19/6/2020
Published 27/8/2020

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.4013308

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Cite this article as:

Aziz R, Nazir S, Anwar A. The way of teaching: perception of medical students in different medical colleges. Int. J. Med. Dent. Allied Health Sci. 2020;2(8). 266-71

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THE WAY OF TEACHING: PERCEPTION OF MEDICAL STUDENTS IN DIFFERENT MEDICAL COLLEGES

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ABSTRACT:

Teaching and learning are active and continuous processes. Teaching is an art of facilitating and supporting learning character in students. However, learning is the cognitive processes whereby an individual acquires the professional and ethical values, the biomedical, behavioral and clinical knowledge, reasoning and psychomotor skills necessary for professional competence. A total of 130 medical and dental students participated in the study. There were 85 males and 45 females. The mean age was 21.78 ± 2.12 years. A total of 65 students told that they would prefer power point presentations, forty-two students replied that blackboard teaching is more understandable, twelve students preferred both power point presentations as well as blackboard and eleven students preferred use of transparencies.

Keyword: Teaching Methodology, Powerpoint presentations, blackboard, transparencies, medical students, dental students

INTRODUCTION:

Teaching and learning are active and continuous processes. Teaching is an art of facilitating and supporting learning character in students. However, learning is the cognitive processes whereby an individual acquires the professional and ethical values, the biomedical, behavioral and clinical knowledge, reasoning and psychomotor skills necessary for professional competence. Furthermore, learning ultimately leads to permanent change in the behavior of the learner. The development of medical education has been described as a history of reform without change. During the past decade, all UK medical schools have implemented reforms to the manifest (overt) undergraduate curriculum, with changes to course content, teaching methods, and examinations. Lectures have been the most common form of teaching and learning since ancient times. Although discussion methods in small groups appear to be a superior method of attaining higher-level intellectual learning, in India it is almost inevitable that medical students will experience lectures, as the number of students attending medical schools is too large in comparison to the teaching staff available. Hence, the lecture is here to stay, so it is immensely important that it should be as effective as possible.

During a lecture, both the visual and auditory senses are used to absorb information and here assistance in the form of a visual aid is useful. A chalkboard is uniquely effective as a medium of classroom instruction and has been used commonly in lectures, while the use of transparencies with an overhead projector is also popular. The once-popular 35-mm slide projector seems to be headed for extinction. Recently the use of electronic presentations has become common and Microsoft PowerPoint is now the most popular package used out of all electronic presentations. According to one study, the medical students in preferred the use of PPT presentations significantly. So students'

preferences for a teaching method can vary greatly within the same institution given the same infrastructure and facilities (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This survey study was conducted among different medical and dental college students. They were asked different questions on predefined proforma. They were asked whether they preferer power point presentations, use of blackboard or transparencies and answer these questions regarding their selection i.e. was the lecture organized, audible, clear, and understandable etc. All the data was analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. Relevant statistical analysis was performed. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

A total of 130 medical and dental students participated in the study. There were 85 males and 45 females. The mean age was 21.78 ± 2.12 years.

A total of 65 students told that they would prefer power point presentations because lectures are more organized and whether it is understandable or not it depends on how the teacher delivers. Forty-two students replied that blackboard teaching is more understandable because teacher is also active and speaks clearly and audibly. Twelve students preferred both power point presentations as well as blackboard. Eleven students preferred use of transparencies while delivering the lectures.

DISCUSSION:

A teaching method is the system of operations and activities of the teacher and his/her students, which help students to acquire knowledge, skills, and abilities, develop capabilities, and form a view of the world. The educational environment is a dynamic and information - intensive space for learning developed and impacted by the educator. It is the duty of the teachers to emphasize these facts during the lecture. Use of teaching media plays an important role in this aspect. Learning and teaching are continuous processes which act simultaneously. This can be demonstrated when learners acquire the ability to express their gained insight, realization, facts, and new skills. A good teaching needs a good communication for exchanging ideas and information. It is a complex process and has five main components viz. source (teacher), receiver (audience/students), message (content/lecture), channels (medium/traditional blackboard, transparencies, and power point presentations), and feedback (effect). The major limitation of lectures is that listener passively receives the material and feels bored and sleepy. Lectures can be made more effective by using visual aids. Blackboard is most commonly used visual aid as it has easy access and relatively simple to use. It needs no special equipment except for chalk, board, and duster which are easily affordable. Moreover, handouts are not given out in advance in blackboard teaching, so the students tend to focus more

intently on the lecturer. Hence, a good lecturer can motivate the students on a journey of discovery, exposing students to one interesting fact after another by blackboard teaching method. Students will have better retention of the subject afterward if the notes are written with the lecturer's explanation. However, blackboard teaching aid may cause note-taking fatigue, especially after continuous and long lectures. In blackboard, teaching can be difficult to catch continuation with the lecturer if student lose focus for even a moment (4-7).

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